

Combining Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials with X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy to Resolve the Structure–Property Relationship in Functional Oxides New

Version 1

Description

DMP outlines general data management principles within the research project: *Combining Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials with X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy to Resolve the Structure–Property Relationship in Functional Oxides*. PostDoc Latvia ERDF project no. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/016. Project leader: Dr. Pjotrs Žguns. Total budget: 185,510 EUR. Project duration: 01.03.2025 - 29.02.2028.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Nr.1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/016

Researchers

Pjotrs Žguns (0000-0002-3387-2919)

Organizations

LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES CIETVIELU FIZIKAS INSTITUTS

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: *Combining Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials with X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy to Resolve the Structure–Property Relationship in Functional Oxides New*

Description:

DMP outlines general data management principles within the research project: *Combining Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials with X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy to Resolve the Structure–Property Relationship in Functional Oxides*. PostDoc Latvia ERDF project no. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/016. Project leader: Dr. Pjotrs Žguns. Total budget: 185,510 EUR. Project duration: 01.03.2025 - 29.02.2028.

Researchers:

Pjotrs Žguns (0000-0002-3387-2919)

Organizations:

LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES CIETVIELU FIZIKAS INSTITUTS

Contact: Žguns Pjotrs (pjotrs.zguns@cfi.lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Nr.1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/016

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: **Public**

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Auxiliary python scripts for fine-tuning of universal Machine Learning Interatomic Potential CHGNet

These scripts are auxiliary tools intended to assist in the fine-tuning of universal machine learning interatomic potentials.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Auxiliary python scripts for fine-tuning of universal Machine Learning Interatomic Potential CHGNet

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)
computational materials scientists

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15585262>

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15585262>

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

MIT License

3 Resources and Security

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

